

Social Media Marketing Strategy for a Leisure Hotel Using Digital Customer Experience Journey Approach: A Study on Inside by Melia Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT: Inside by Melia Yogyakarta is a 4-star business and leisure hotel owned by PT. Saraswanti Indoland Development. In 2018-2019, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta experienced a relatively rapid increase in revenue. However, the Directors of PT Saraswanti Indoland Development are still not satisfied with the hotel's current performance. To improve hotel performance, the target market will be focused on leisure travelers. However, the social media platform owned by Inside by Melia Yogyakarta, which will attract leisure travelers, also does not have a good performance. To overcome this issue, several analyzes and findings are conducted. External analysis is determined by PESTEL and Competitor Analysis. Internal analysis is determined by VRIO and Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP). Then, a survey was carried out to find out the preferences of leisure travelers. The survey was made based on the customer experience's digital journey while staying at Inside by Melia Yogyakarta and hotels in the Yogyakarta. There are six stages of the customer experience journey: the awareness/inspiration stage; research/consideration stage; decision-making stage; preparation stage; in-hotel experience stage; and loyalty advocacy stage. The survey results were processed quantitatively and analyzed descriptively. Based on the survey results, the root of the problem lies in customers' low awareness/inspiration towards Inside by Melia Yogyakarta's social media. The solution to this problem is sought by using the Repositioning and New Wave Marketing strategy to create a horizontal marketing system on Inside by Melia Yogyakarta's social media. Each alternative solution is systematically compiled on the customer journey map. then recommendations for social media content were made to implement the formulated strategy.

KEYWORDS: Customer Experience Journey, Digital Marketing, Hotel, New Wave Marketing, Repositioning

I. INTRODUCTION

The Special Region of Yogyakarta is a province that has many exciting tourism potentials to visit. The number of foreign and domestic tourist visits to the Special Region of Yogyakarta is increasing every year. This potential causes the hotel industry to develop rapidly in the Special Region of Yogyakarta (Hendriyati, 2019). Technological advances such as social media have played a role in the hospitality industry's development in this era. Social media can change the way travelers search, discover, and share information about travel experiences and decide which hotels to stay (Varkaris and Neuhofer, 2017).

Inside by Melia Yogyakarta is a 4-star hotel operated by Melia Hotels International. This hotel was established in Yogyakarta in 2017 and is the first hotel to use the Inside by Melia brand in the Asia Pacific. Inside by Melia Yogyakarta carries a design in a chic and trendy with an urban lifestyle touch with the concept of "Holistic Bleisure," which is a combination of business and leisure trips. This hotel is convenient for those who enjoy work, life, leisure, and business moments.

In 2018-2019, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta experienced a relatively rapid increase in revenue. However, the board of directors of PT Saraswanti Indoland Development is still not satisfied with the hotel performance because their income is still inferior to competing hotels in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Currently, most hotel guests who stay are from the business travelers segment. Because each year, more of the leisure travelers segment travel to Yogyakarta than business travelers, the hotel target market will be adjusted on leisure travelers to improve hotel revenue performance. However, this effort is hampered because the social media platform owned by Inside by Melia Yogyakarta has less impact on increasing hotel guests' number for the leisure travelers segment. Therefore, this research was conducted with a customer experience journey approach to solve problems experienced in Inside by Melia Yogyakarta's social media.

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The objectives of this study are: (1) To find out the strategy that needs to be done when Inside by Melia Yogyakarta has to do repositioning, (2) To find out the suitable strategic plan for Inside by Melia Yogyakarta social media content to customers awareness and attractiveness, (3) To design an effective journey through social media content for the potential customer from the leisure travelers segment, (4) To design an effective experience through social media content for existing customers from the leisure travelers segment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

To overcome this issue, several analyzes and findings are conducted. External analysis is determined by PESTEL and Competitor Analysis. Internal analysis is determined by VRIO and Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP).

According to Gupta (2013), PESTEL analysis is a framework or tool to analyze and monitor the external marketing environmental factors. The purpose of conducting PESTEL analysis in this research is to identify the external factors and uncertainty factors that affect the hotel industry. (1) The analysis of political points shows that the Indonesian government supports the development of Yogyakarta's tourism industry. An example that shows this commitment, the passing of Presidential Regulation No.3 of 2016. The government is committed to developing ten tourist destinations, and Borobudur Temple is included in the development list. The policy was continued with one of the Strategic Goals of the Tourism Sector 2020-2024 points, namely, the government supports the development of Borobur - Joglosemar tourism (Yogyakarta, Solo, and Semarang). (2) In the analysis of economic points, the Indonesian economy shows a positive trend that encourages growth in the tourism sector. The millennial generation is the generation that has significantly contributed to the growth of the tourism sector. This generation is causing a shift from goods-based consumption to experience-based consumption. (3) In analyzing social points from the demographic approach, Indonesian tourism is supported by the productive age population (15–64 years). Most (46.3%) online travel booking services in Indonesia are between 25 and 34, who are millennials. (4) In the analysis of technology points, there have been advances in technological developments such as increasing online travel bookings through various platforms and contributing to Indonesian tourism. (5) In the analysis of environmental points, ecotourism is tourism in Indonesia, which is in great demand and has a low impact on nature tourism. (6) In the analysis of legal points, Law Number 13 of 2003 concerning the Manpower Act affects Indonesia's hotel industry. The hotel industry is allowed to hire employees on a three months trial period on absolute term contracts. This policy supports the hotel industry being able to hire the right employees.

Based on Competitor analysis, there are four hotels in the Yogyakarta that are considered competitors to Inside by Melia Yogyakarta. These four hotels are considered competitors based on having the same target market, stars, and the same number of rooms and facilities. The four hotels are the Sheraton Hotel Mustika Yogyakarta Resort & Spa, Novotel Yogyakarta, Sahid Jaya Yogyakarta Hotel & Convention, and Grand Mercure Yogyakarta Adi Sucipto. Overall, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta is in a middle position when compared to its competitor hotels. However, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta needs to improve social media performance. Based on the number of followers, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta is inferior to other hotels and is only relatively equal to Sahid Hotel Yogyakarta.

According to Rothaermel (2013), VRIO is an acronym for Valuable (V), Rare (R), Imitate (I), and Organization (O). The VRIO framework is used to analyze the implications of corporate resources on competitiveness. Resources Inside by Melia Yogyakarta is divided into 2, tangible and intangible. In terms of tangible resources, most of the resources have a competitive parity impact, which indicates that Inside by Melia Yogyakarta resources is not a rare thing in the hospitality world. Then for intangible resources, most of them have a temporary competitive parity impact. This urban lifestyle hotel is still rare in Yogyakarta but easy to imitate.

According to Kotler and Keller (2009), Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) is a framework that companies can use to identify their consumers accurately and formulate them in the form of product positions in consumers' eyes. The Inside by Melia Yogyakarta target market are Business and Leisure Travelers from the millennial generation (26-40 years). The positioning of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta is "Urban Lifestyle Hotels for Business and Leisure Travelers."

III. METHODOLOGY

After the internal, external analysis have been carried out, the survey was made to find out leisure travelers preferences. The survey was made based on the customer experience's digital journey while staying at Inside by Melia and Yogyakarta hotels. The conceptual framework can be seen in Figure 1.

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Research at Inside by Melia Yogyakarta was conducted using two methods: qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative research methods are research types that produce findings that can not be obtained using statistical procedures or other means of quantification/measurement. This research conducted a qualitative research method through interviews. Interviews were conducted during exploratory business issues and understand deeper hotel conditions.

Quantitative research methods involve measuring a specific feature's level and processing with certain statistical calculations. This research conducted a quantitative research method through a survey with a tool in the form of an online questionnaire distributed randomly to obtain respondents. The answers obtained from respondents will be processed quantitatively using SPSS. The statistical method used is the t-test. A T-test is a statistical test used to compare two groups means (Kim, 2015).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

After the questionnaire answers from all respondents have been fulfilled, the respondent will be divided into three personas. (1) Persona 1 (existing customer) is a respondent who is aware of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta and has stayed overnight. (2) Persona 2 (potential customer) is a respondent who is aware of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta but has never stayed overnight. (3) Persona 3 (potential customer) is a respondent who is not aware of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta and has never stayed overnight.

IV. FINDINGS AND ARGUMENT

Based on the results of a comparative analysis of each stage of the journey between Persona 1 (existing customer) and Persona 2 and 3 (potential customer), it can be concluded that the main problem of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta when changing their positioning to hotels for leisure travelers is the awareness stage. The problem at this awareness stage affects other journey.

The descriptive analysis results from the survey show that Persona 1 members (existing customers) can find out the Inside by Melia Yogyakarta in a traditional/vertical way. In terms of ranking, the touchpoints that most influenced Persona 1 members' awareness of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta were word of mouth from parent sources. The following sources of influence are siblings and hotel signboard. The source of social media contact points is only in seventh place.

It is different from Persona 2 and 3 (potential customers), which can be aware of hotels in Yogyakarta digitally/horizontal way. Three touchpoints that influence Persona 2 to become aware of hotels in Yogyakarta are the internet media. The first place is social media. Then OTA and media feedback. Likewise, with Persona 3, the first order of the most influential touchpoints comes from social media, then media feedback and OTA.

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This difference in touchpoint affects each persona's duration to be aware of Inside by Melia Yogyakarta and hotels in Yogyakarta. Inside by Melia Yogyakarta needs to be recognized by customers for 2-3 weeks to more than one month. Meanwhile, hotels in the Special Region of Yogyakarta take one day to one week to be recognized by people in an excellent digital way.

Millennials who are existing and potential customers choose to use social media on Instagram to be aware of hotels. Other social media used are Twitter and Tiktok. On Instagram social media, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta needs to take advantage of the Instagram story feature properly, such as spending attention to posting time and content. Besides, Inside by Melia Yogyakarta needs to place Instagram Advertisement because Instagram Advertisement are an influential Instagram feature to make each persona aware.

Figure 2. Root Cause Analysis

The social media content created by Inside by Melia is less relevant to what potential and existing customers want. The content that potential customers want to be aware of hotel social media is good photos and video visuals; engaging influencers; and content about tourism and culinary in Yogyakarta. The content currently posted by the Inside by Melia social media is more suitable for maintaining existing customers (promo content and facilities). However, existing customers are also less interested in the social media of Inside by Melia because the quality of photos and videos is not good and influencers are not quite right.

According to Kartajaya (2010), New Wave Marketing strategy is the right strategy to solve awareness problem on social media. It can change the vertical marketing method of Inside by Melia to horizontal marketing. When using the New Wave strategy, segmentation will be changed to a more horizontal direction by communitization consumers as a group of people who care about each other and have the same purposes, values, and identity. This community must be positioned as the center of the Inside by Melia's business strategy. Besides, these communities are also maintained with influencers following the DNA of Inside by Melia, which follows the preferences of each Persona. Inside by Melia has DNA as an urban lifestyle hotel for leisure travelers. Everything customers are looking for in Yogyakarta can be found at Inside by Melia. Communities recommended by the author, such as music, handicrafts, motorbikes, and food and beverage, are communities that describe the character of Yogyakarta and can be found at Inside by Melia.

Therefore, the way to attract potential customers to Inside by Melia's social media is by improving the visual photos and video content first. Then hire influencers according to their preferences (tourism and culinary). Then, form or collaborate with the community according to the DNA Inside by Melia and customers interest. The way to maintain existing customers through experience within social media is to keep a two-way relationship between Inside by Melia and existing customers. Involve them

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in many things. Maintain the credibility of DNA Inside by Melia. Then create a new experience at Inside by Melia by involving the community and existing customers so that they have a reason to return to stay.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The difference in the awareness process between Persona 1 (existing customers) and Persona 2 and 3 (potential customers) shows that Inside by Melia has problems with its digital marketing. Therefore, when Inside by Melia decided to focus on re-positioning the hotel for leisure travelers from the millennial generation, touchpoints in selecting social media platforms, the features used, and the content created needed to be better planned. New Wave Marketing strategy is the right strategy to solve awareness problem on social media. It can change the vertical marketing method of Inside by Melia to horizontal marketing. Segmentation will be changed to a more horizontal direction by communitization consumers as a group of people who care about each other and have the same purposes, values, and identity. This community must be positioned as the center of the Inside by Melia's business strategy.

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